

Nonlinear low-velocity impact response of sandwich beams with functionally graded negative Poisson's ratio honeycomb core

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Introduction

- In recent years, **auxetic materials** have attracted considerable attention because their novel property of shrinking when compressed, i.e. they have **negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)**. Furthermore, the NPR material has shown great potentials to be **the ideal core of sandwich structures**, which are widely used in aerospace, ship, automobile industry.
- **Functionally graded materials (FGMs)** are a new generation of composite materials where the microstructural details are varied in a spatially pattern. Functionally graded honeycomb-like cellular structures are characterized by a **gradual variation of cell size, shape or wall thickness** over a prescribed volume. The gradient configuration could lead to a **continuous distribution of curvatures, stiffness and energy absorption capability**.
- In the present work, we focus our attention on the nonlinear low-velocity impact response of sandwich beams with FG-NPR honeycomb core. The novelty of this study is that **the NPR core and functionally graded pattern are both taken into account**. 3D full scale finite element simulations are conducted.
- **The core is arranged to have an out-of-plane direction as Y-direction, which is different from that of the sandwich beam (Z-direction)**, as shown in **Fig. 1**. In such a layout, when the sandwich beam is subjected to an out-of-plane impact, the auxetic core will response in an in-plane NPR behavior.
- The sandwich beam has a length-to-thickness of 10, and a width of 6mm. The core has cell wall thickness of 0.1mm, and a total height of 24mm, the material of which are assumed as Ti-4V-6Al. And the face-sheets have the same material of Aluminum and thickness of 0.3mm, and are arranged to share nodes with core along their interfaces.

FE Modelling

Results

Concluding Remarks

- As illustrated in **Fig. 1**, when the sandwich beam is subjected to an out-of-plane impact, **the core materials in the region close to the impact area will "flow" towards mid-span cross section**, which indicate that in this volume the strain along the X-direction $\epsilon_1 < 0$. Meanwhile, the strain along thickness direction (Z-direction) $\epsilon_3 < 0$, the effective Poisson's ratio is therefore $\nu_{31} = -\epsilon_1/\epsilon_3 < 0$.
- The indentation-time curves of sandwich beams with different FG cores are presented in **Fig. 2**, in which the indentation denotes the thickness decrease (δh) of the mid-span cross-section. Firstly, the **thickness decrease of the sandwich beams with UD (-20°) honeycomb core is distinctly smaller than that of UD (+20°) beam**, which indicate that the impact resistance of the former one is higher than that of the latter one. Furthermore, the difference between different configurations with NPR is evidently, from which in can be concluded that the FG configuration can bring significant effect on the nonlinear low-velocity response of sandwich beams. Moreover, **the FG-V beam (as shown in Fig. 1) has the lowest curve**, meaning a highest impact resistance.
- In conclusion, the **NPR characteristic** of core can remarkably reduce the thickness decrease of sandwich beams when subjected to an out-of-plane impact, and the **FG configurations** will distinctly influence the impact response.
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